

PREVALENCE OF HAMSTRING FLEXIBILITY AMONG PROFESSIONAL PHYSIOTHERAPISTS AND ITS RELATION TO LOW BACK PAIN

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Abstract

Background: Muscular and skeletal pain affects approximately half of physical therapists within five years. Early age physical therapists experience early pain due to inexperience with intervention positions. Most physical therapists develop muscular and skeletal injuries before thirty. These impairments affect the back and leg muscles, cervical area, shoulders, hands, wrists, and knees. **Objectives:** The objective of this study was to find of hamstring flexibility in professional physiotherapist. Secondly to determine the association of low back pain with hamstring flexibility. **Material and methods:** A random sample of 80 professional physical therapists from Allied Hospital, Faisalabad, District Headquarter Hospital, Faisalabad, Madina Teaching Hospital Faisalabad was considered. After signing the consent form, therapist assessed participants by active knee extension test for measuring hamstring flexibility. Generally, angle below 20 degrees are considered normal. If the tightness is between 21 and 30 degrees, it was considered mild; between 31 and 40 degrees, it is considered moderate; and over 40 degrees, it was considered severe. Then low back pain assessed by numeric pain rating scale to find association between hamstring flexibility and incidence of low back pain. **Methods:** A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 80 physiotherapists from hospitals in Faisalabad. Hamstring flexibility was evaluated using the Active Knee Extension (AKE) test. LBP was assessed via the Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) and Oswestry Low Back Disability Index (ODI). Data were analyzed using SPSS 20 with chi-square tests. **Results:** 77.5% participants exhibited hamstring tightness. Significant association was found between hamstring tightness and LBP ($p < 0.05$). The mean NPRS score was 4.50 ± 1.62 , indicating moderate pain, and the mean ODI score was 16.36 ± 8.94 , indicating moderate disability. **Conclusion:** Hamstring tightness is prevalent among physiotherapists and significantly associated with low back pain and disability

INTRODUCTION

Flexibility is an essential component of health and fitness that is necessary for the best possible functioning of the musculoskeletal system and the

highest possible level of effectiveness in physical activities. The capacity of a muscle to elongate and the ability of a joint to move through a range of

motion are both aspects of flexibility. The ability of an individual's muscles to be flexible enables seamless movement, which increases both protection and the potential for optimum physical exercise (1). Musculoskeletal ailments brought on by workplace activities are referred to as work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs). These conditions are frequent in occupations involving physical labor, carrying heavy loads, or repeating motions, and they might result in shifts to working practices, less hours employed, or alterations to the type of employment (3). Repeating motions, unsuitable surroundings, and increased job stress are the main risk factors linked to job-related musculoskeletal illnesses. The greatest prevalence of muscular and skeletal symptoms was among medical practitioners, particularly those who had frequent interactions with their patients. Despite having considerable understanding of musculoskeletal problems and preventative measures, physical therapists nevertheless run the danger of job-related accidents (3).

Clinicians are at chance for both acute and long-term work-related musculoskeletal disorders as a result of these occupational duties (2, 4). According to statistics, WMSDs are very common amongst physiotherapists, with lifelong incidence rates of 55-91% and 12-month incidence rate of 40-91.3%. (4). The possibility of job accidents is greater for physical therapists because they treat a significant number of clients in a single day. The frequency of these work-related diseases is significantly influenced by the specialties of physical therapists (such as orthopedics, neurology, etc.), employment environment, their age (3).

Numerous events contributes to low back pain that include enhanced lumbar lordotic curve, decreased abdominal muscular wall length and power, reduced back extensor muscular strength, decreased iliopsoas length, reduced hamstrings flexibility, body mass, etc. Hamstrings are part of the core musculature (lumbar & pelvic and hip complex), and stiffness may decrease the lower back lordotic curvature, impacting body position, range of motion, and the risk of low back pain (5). According to literature approximately 71 percent persons reported hamstrings stiffness (6). Tight hamstrings are not only one of the causes of a limited range of motion, but they can also contribute

to a variety of other musculoskeletal issues (8). A lack of flexibility creates a vicious circle that results in a reduction in range of motion and an increase in the number of postural problems. Stiff muscles also cause blood arteries to become compressed, which results in decreased optimum performance (9). There is a correlation between hamstring stiffness and the emergence of plantar fasciitis, patellofemoral pain syndrome and patellar tendinopathy (11).

Stiff hamstrings are linked to a malfunctioning motor control pattern, which in turn leads to a submaximal activation pattern of postural muscles, which in turn causes the hamstrings to function as stabilisers rather than as their primary function, which is to act as prime movers. Because of this shift in fundamental function, some people experience stiffness in their hamstrings (12).

One of the primary reasons for the prevalence of positional abnormalities in today's culture is the contemporary trend towards lethargic modes of living. The protracted seating hours that are necessary in most professions and educational settings can have an adverse effect on the elasticity of soft tissues, particularly the muscles that are found in the joints (9).

Hamstrings arise from the inferomedial impression on the upper ischial tuberosity and attach on the upper posterior edge of the tibia. Hamstrings stiffness causes a dorsal pelvis tilt and lessens lumbar lordotic curve, causing low back pain (5). Hamstring tightness reduces pelvic movement. Vertebral abnormalities and kinematic modifications in pressure distribution result. Poor hamstrings extensibility is linked to thoracic kyphotic, spondylolysis, disc herniation, lumbar and pelvic rhythm adjustments, and low back pain (LBP). Slightly shorter hamstrings also affect gait, fall risk, muscular & skeletal accidents and cause problems with dynamic balance (14, 15). Isometric length-tension relationship states that muscle fibers enlarged further than maximum length generate less effective tension. Dorsal pelvic tilting may extend back extensor musculatures attached to the pelvis. Back extensors work harder. Long-term pulling of relatively short musculature weakens and exhausts lumbar musculatures. Low back pain may result from back extensor muscle fatigue overloading spine soft tissue and inert composition (16, 17).

Because of the stiffness in the hamstrings, there are several complications that can develop. The majority of the biomechanical research on the function of the hamstrings shows that the hamstrings reach their maximum length at the final moment of the swing phase of the gait, just before foot contact. This is also the time whenever the hip is flexed and the knee flexion is decreasing, both of which can be affected in individuals who have hamstring tightness. It is possible for it to create a posterior pelvis inclination, which in turn leads to a flat back position, which, if not corrected, can result in low back discomfort (13). The prevention of acute and persistent musculoskeletal injuries and back muscles problems, as well as positional abnormalities, movement restriction, and the risk of stumbling can be achieved by maintaining flexibility in the hamstrings and the low back. The patellofemoral joint dysfunction, pelvic discomfort, LBP, and positional abnormalities all contribute to the length of the hamstring muscles and the measurement of their length. When present in people of advanced age, constricted hamstrings can shorten footfall length and slow walking speed, both of which can result in difficulties with dynamic equilibrium (18).

Studies that showed a positive correlation between hamstring tightness and the intensity of low back pain also found a relationship between hamstring tightness and mechanical low back pain. This association was noted in both of the studies (19). Because tight hamstring muscles prevent an anterior inclination of the sacrum during spinal abduction, this causes increased tension in the lumbar region's muscles and ligaments, which in turn results in substantially greater compressive stresses being placed on the lumbar spine (20).

Given the critical role physiotherapists play in patient rehabilitation, it is imperative to address factors that may impair their own musculoskeletal health. This study aims to evaluate the prevalence of hamstring flexibility among professional physiotherapists and determine its relationship with low back pain, thereby contributing to the formulation of preventive strategies.

METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional study was conducted among eighty professional physiotherapists aged between 22

and 50 years working in Allied Hospital, District Headquarter Hospital, and Madina Teaching Hospital, Faisalabad. Participants were selected through simple random sampling. Professional physiotherapists who worked at least 6 to 8 hours daily and provided informed consent were included. Individuals with a history of fractures, surgeries involving the back, pelvis, hips, or knees, those experiencing radiating pain, pregnant women, and professional athletes were excluded.

Hamstring flexibility was assessed using the Active Knee Extension (AKE) test, which has been validated for reliability with intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs) ranging from 0.87 to 0.94 (Neto T et al., 2015). Participants were positioned supine with the hip and knee flexed at 90 degrees. A goniometer was used to measure the angle at the knee joint as the participant actively extended the knee. An extension angle of $\leq 20^\circ$ was considered normal; $21-30^\circ$ indicated mild tightness; $31-40^\circ$ indicated moderate tightness; and $>40^\circ$ indicated severe tightness. Low back pain was assessed using the Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS), a reliable and valid tool for evaluating pain intensity in musculoskeletal conditions (Hrvatini I, Puh U, 2021). Participants rated their pain on a scale from 0 (no pain) to 10 (worst imaginable pain). Disability related to low back pain was measured using the Oswestry Low Back Disability Index (ODI), a widely used instrument with established reliability and construct validity for patients with chronic low back pain (Lee CP et al., 2017). Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic data. The chi-square test was employed to determine the association between hamstring tightness and the presence of low back pain, with a significance level set at $p \leq 0.05$.

RESULTS

A total of 80 professional physiotherapists participated in the study. The age of participants ranged from 22 to 46 years, with a mean age of 27.00 years (SD = 4.587), the sample consisted of 63.8% females and 36.3% males. Out of 80 participants, 62 (77.5%) were found to have hamstring tightness (knee extension angle $>20^\circ$), while 18 (22.5%) exhibited normal hamstring flexibility (knee extension angle $\leq 20^\circ$). Among the 62 participants

with hamstring tightness, the mean knee extension angle of the **left leg** was 36.31° (SD = 10.81), and for the **right leg**, it was 37.10° (SD = 10.72), indicating a moderate degree of tightness in both legs.

Association Between Hamstring Tightness and Low Back Pain

Among those with hamstring tightness (n=62), 69.4% (n=43) reported experiencing low back pain, whereas only 5.6% (n=1) of the 18 participants without hamstring tightness reported low back pain. A Chi-square test was conducted to examine the association between hamstring tightness and low back pain, revealing a statistically significant

relationship ($\chi^2 = 22.942$, $df = 1$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that participants with hamstring tightness were significantly more likely to report low back pain

Intensity of Low Back Pain and Disability

Among participants who reported low back pain (n=44), the mean score on the **Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS)** was 4.50 (SD = 1.621), indicating moderate pain intensity additionally, the mean score on the **Oswestry Low Back Disability Index (ODI)** was 16.36 (SD = 8.945), also suggesting a moderate level of disability among these individuals.

In participants who were positive for presences of hamstring tightness, mean hamstring tightness of left leg reported to be 36.3±10.8 showing moderate level of hamstring tightness in left leg of physiotherapist having minimum range of 21° and maximum range of 62°. While for right leg mean hamstring tightness reported to be 37.09±10.7 showing moderate level of hamstring tightness having minimum range of 21°

and maximum range of 65°. Among participants who have Positive (angle > 20°) hamstring tightness 69.4% reported having complain of low back pain while 30.6% does not reported low back pain. In contrast participants who were negative (angle $\leq 20^\circ$) for hamstring tightness also reported low back pain but in low proportion (5.6%).

Table 1. Association between low back pain and hamstring tightness

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	22.942 ^a	1	.000
Continuity Correction ^b	20.437	1	.000
Likelihood Ratio	25.965	1	.000

Linear-by-Linear Association	22.655	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	80		

Above table displays association between hamstring tightness and occurrence of low back pain. As chi-square test was conducted to find the association and $p \leq 0.05$ it shows there is strong association between them.

In participants who were positive for presences of low back pain, mean LBP reported to be 4.50 ± 1.621 showing moderate level of pain ranging between minimum level of 1 to maximum level of 8 points pain. In participants who have complain of low back pain, mean ODI presented to be 16.36 ± 8.945 as shown in above table showing moderate level of disability ranging between minimum level of 2 to maximum level of 34 points.

DISCUSSION

Koley and Likhi (21) Study also utilized the modified Oswestry Pain Questionnaire as a tool to evaluate the intensity of low back pain among the participants. The measurement of hamstring flexibility was conducted by utilizing a goniometer to assess the active knee extension on both sides, similar to current study. They results suggest that there wasn't a significant association between hamstring flexibility and low back pain. Further research may be necessary to confirm these findings and explore potential alternative factors that may contribute to low back pain (21). But in contrast current study challenged their results as in current study significant association between hamstring tightness and low back pain was found.

Current study results were in line with pervious researches by using same outcome measure tools (19). Radwan, et al., in 2015 conducted research to determine the degree to which individuals have varying degrees of hamstring flexibility and whether or not this has a connection to the intensity of low back pain. Hamstring length was measured by active knee extension test by using a standard goniometer. There is a possibility that moderate mechanical LBP and stiffness in the hamstring are related to one another. It was discovered that the stiffness a patient felt was directly correlated to the level of LBP pain that patient encounter (19). Similarly 77.5% of physiotherapists have moderate

level of hamstring tightness causing moderate level of pain in low back. Significant association was found between hamstring tightness and low back pain ($p < .005$) in current study results.

Current study results are in contrast to Sweeney, Daoud (27). Sweeney, et al. in 2019 investigated the correlation between low back pain (LBP), flexibility in adolescent female gymnasts who participate in competitive gymnastics. The prevalence of low back pain appears to be higher among gymnasts, while there does not appear to be a correlation between limited joint flexibility and LBP within this particular group (27).

While current study results are in line with Batool, Muaz (6), even their outcome measure tools are also same resulting same conclusion about hamstring tightness prevalence and association with LBP. Batool, et al. in 2019 investigated potential relationship between chronic low back pain (LBP) and hamstring tightness in professionals. The Oswestry Disability Questionnaire was utilised to assess the percentage of disability among various professionals in a research study. The AKE test was employed to assess hamstring tightness in the research study. The research findings indicate that a significant proportion of individuals with moderate disability experience hamstring tightness, with 28% of respondents reporting this symptom. The study suggests that individuals from various occupations who experience back pain may have tight hamstring muscles (6).

Current study results are in with SAREEN and PRAKASH (5). Sareen And Prakash in 2021 conducted a study to finding the occurrence of hamstrings tightness in young Orthopedic Surgeons. While current study focused on professional physiotherapists. The Active knee extension test was used to assess hamstring flexibility similar to current study, but in current study low back pain and disability was also used as measure of interest. A study found 12.9% had no bilateral hamstrings stiffness. The others had hamstrings stiffness. Both sides had hamstrings tightness. Right side stiffness averaged 30.83 degrees and left side 31.11 degrees (5). While in current study 25.5% have normal

hamstring length while 77.5% have varying degree of hamstring tightness. Mean hamstring tightness of left leg reported to be $36.3^{\circ} \pm 10.8$ showing moderate level of hamstring tightness in left leg of physiotherapist. While for right leg mean hamstring tightness reported to be $37.09^{\circ} \pm 10.7$ showing moderate level of hamstring tightness

The findings of this study indicate a correlation between hamstring tightness, low back pain, and low back disability in physiotherapists. However, it is crucial to recognise the study's constraints and explore other possible interpretations. In conclusion, for a deeper knowledge of the association between tightness in the hamstrings and low back pain, future research should consider adopting a longitudinal design, including diverse populations, utilising comprehensive measures, and accounting for potential confounding factors.

CONCLUSION

Professional physiotherapist suffers from moderate level of hamstring tightness which caused pain in low back of moderate level and there is a significant correlation between hamstring tightness and low back pain, resulting in moderate level of disability in physiotherapists.

REFERENCE

1. Weerasekara I, Kumari I, Weerarathna N, Withanage C, Wanniarachchi C. The prevalence of hamstring tightness among the male athletes of university of peradeniya. *J Palliative Care Med.* 2013 Jan 31;1(108):2.
2. Rahimi F, Kazemi K, Zahednejad S, López-López D, Calvo-Lobo C. Prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal disorders in Iranian physical therapists: a cross-sectional study. *Journal of manipulative and physiological therapeutics.* 2018 Jul 1;41(6):503-7.
3. Milhem M, Kalichman L, Ezra D, Alperovitch-Najenson D. Work-related musculoskeletal disorders among physical therapists: A comprehensive narrative review. *International journal of occupational medicine and environmental health.* 2016 July 4;29(5):735-47.

4. SAREEN A, PRAKASH J. Prevalence of Hamstring Tightness in Young Orthopaedic Surgeons. *Journal of Clinical & Diagnostic Research.* 2021 Jun 1;15(6).
5. Batool F, Muaaz F, Tariq K, Sarfraz N. Relationship of chronic LBP (low back pain) with hamstring tightness in professionals. *Journal of Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences.* 2019 Oct 9;18(03):236-40.
6. Houston MN, Hodson VE, Adams KK, Hoch JM. The effectiveness of whole-body-vibration training in improving hamstring flexibility in physically active adults. *Journal of sport rehabilitation.* 2015 Feb 1;24(1):77-82.
7. Vidhi S, Anuprita T, Asmita K, Twinkle D, Unnati P, Sujata Y. Comparison of PNF technique with NDS technique for hamstrings tightness in asymptomatic subjects. *Indian Journal of Physiotherapy and Occupational Therapy.* 2014 Jul 1;8(3):158.
8. Kage V, Ratnam R. Immediate effect of active release technique versus mulligan bent leg raise in subjects with hamstring tightness: a randomized clinical trial. *Int J Physiother Res.* 2014 Feb 11;2(1):301-4.
9. Fatima G, Qamar MM, Hassan JU, Basharat A. Extended sitting can cause hamstring tightness. *Saudi Journal of Sports Medicine.* 2017 May 1;17(2):110.
10. Mistry GS, Vyas NJ, Sheth MS. Comparison of hamstrings flexibility in subjects with chronic low back pain versus normal individuals. *J Clin Exp Res.* 2014 Jan 1;2(1):85.
11. Koli BK, Anap DB. Prevalence and severity of hamstring tightness among college student: A cross sectional study. *International Journal of Clinical and Biomedical Research.* 2018 Apr 15:65-8.
12. KAMANI N, ZALAVADIYA J, NAR N, KAKKAD A. A STUDY TO FIND OUT RELATION BETWEEN HAMSTRINGS FLEXIBILITY AND BACK EXTENSORS ENDURANCE IN HEALTHY FEMALE PHYSIOTHERAPY STUDENTS: AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY. *Indian Journal of Physical Therapy.* 2016 Jun 1;4(1):10-5.

13. Naqvi R, Arshad N, Imran M, Aftab AA, Batool S. Prevalence of hamstring tightness among university students in Lahore, Pakistan. *Rawal Medical Journal*. 2019 Jan 12;44(4):853-5.
14. Thakur D, Rose S. A study to find out the correlation between the right and left hamstring length in both genders to determine the prevalence of hamstring tightness among college students. *Journal of Health and Allied Sciences NU*. 2016 Dec 1;6(04):46-52.
15. Radwan A, Bigney KA, Buonomo HN, Jarmak MW, Moats SM, Ross JK, et al. Evaluation of intra-subject difference in hamstring flexibility in patients with low back pain: An exploratory study. *Journal of back and musculoskeletal rehabilitation*. 2015 Jan 1;28(1):61-6.
16. Nishikawa Y, Aizawa J, Kanemura N, Takahashi T, Hosomi N, Maruyama H, et al. Immediate effect of passive and active stretching on hamstrings flexibility: a single-blinded randomized control trial. *J Phys Ther Sci*. 2015;27(10):3167-70.
17. Koley S, Likhi N. No relationship between low back pain and hamstring flexibility. *The Anthropologist*. 2011 Apr 1;13(2):117-20.
18. Sadler SG, Spink MJ, Ho A, De Jonge XJ, Chuter VH. Restriction in lateral bending range of motion, lumbar lordosis, and hamstring flexibility predicts the development of low back pain: a systematic review of prospective cohort studies. *BMC musculoskeletal disorders*. 2017 Dec 1;18(179):1-15.
19. Neto T, Jacobsohn L, Carita AI, Oliveira R. Reliability of the Active-Knee-Extension and Straight-Leg-Raise Tests in Subjects With Flexibility Deficits. *J Sport Rehabil*. 2015 Dec 3;24(4):1-12.
20. Hrvatin I, Puh U. Measurement properties of the numerical pain rating scale in patients with musculoskeletal impairments of the limbs—a systematic literature review. *Zdrav Vestn*. 2021 Oct 1;90(1):9-10.
21. Lee C-P, Fu T-S, Liu C-Y, Hung C-I. Psychometric evaluation of the Oswestry Disability Index in patients with chronic low back pain: factor and Mokken analyses. *Health and quality of life outcomes*. 2017 Dec 1;15(1):1-7.
22. Sweeney EA, Daoud AK, Potter MN, Ritchie L, Howell DR. Association between flexibility and low back pain in female adolescent gymnasts. *Clinical Journal of Sport Medicine*. 2019 Sept 1;29(5):379-83.